

SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC ESTIMATION OF REDUCING SUGAR IN FOOD PRODUCT

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Abstract. *The spectrophotometric method offers an easy, less time consuming, sensitive analysis, by using simple and available reagents, used for determination of concentration of substances. Therefore, spectrophotometric analysis is one of the major interests of analytical laboratories. This work represents the determination of reducing sugar level in jam by spectrophotometric method. A number of reactions between sugars and other chemical reagents produce colored products; the intensity of color related to the initial concentration of sugar. The absorbance of sample solutions measured and compared to the absorbance of standard solutions of known sugar concentrations. Only a limited number of color-change reactions known for polysaccharides, and most involve simple sugars, usually reducing sugars. Glucose sugars chosen primarily because its activity has widespread appeal. Mass concentration is the value read off the calibration curve. In our experiment, Sample 1 and Sample 2, Mass of the reducing sugar have been found to be 0.8 g and 0.5 g.*

Keywords: *spectrophotometer, food product, reducing sugar, hydrolysis, DNSA reagent.*

Introduction

In the food product, sugar is regarded as one of the most significant food ingredients. All kinds of fruits, vegetables, whole grains, and dairy products naturally contain sugars. These sugars are referred to as neutral sugars, or carbs, and they are a vital micronutrient. Sugar comes in two varieties reducing sugar and non-reducing sugar. A sugar that can transfer an electron to another molecule is referred to as a reducing agent in the chemical community and is called a "reducing sugar." The presence causes the reducing sugar group, such as aldehyde or keto, to emerge and change into a sugar with a reducing property. The reducing sugars are maltose, lactose, and glucose. When sugar reduction is combined with other molecules, the oxidation-reduction chemical process takes place. The Somogyi-Nelson Method and the DNS method are commonly used for quantitative sugar reduction [1-5]. The way that beams and other wavelengths are absorbed and processed by substances is analyzed using spectroscopy. It is the study of how materials react to infrared radiation. When using spectrometry, an electromagnetic energy wave passes through a sample, and the interactions between the photon and the sample can affect the binding energies and electrons in the sample. Several types of spectroscopies are available, and crucial facts are obtained through the use of spectrum radiation and absorbance. Aldehyde or keto groups, which are reducing sugars, come into being and change into a sugar having reduction

properties. As a result, the aldoses groups in reducing sugar functions as a reduction agent, losing electrons. The DNS approach is commonly used for quantifying decreasing sugar. The existence of the liberated carbonyl carbon (C=O) in reducing sugars is examined using the Dinitrosalicylic (DNS) spectrophotometric technique, as well as the existence of oxidized of the aldehyde substituents is implicated. In an alkaline environment, 3,5-dinitrosalicylic acid is changed into 3-amino, 5-dinitrosalicylic acid. Moreover, the color's intensity rises as the sugar concentration does. The Dinitrosalicylic acid technique (DNS) and the ultraviolet-visible double beam spectrophotometer (UV-Vis or UV/Vis), which analyses transmittance and computes the ratio of two intensities, were also utilized in this study to find the reducing sugars in the food product.

A number of reactions between sugars and other chemical reagents produce colored products; the intensity of color related to the initial concentration of sugar. The absorbance of sample solutions measured and compared to the absorbance of standard solutions of known sugar concentrations. Only a limited number of color-change reactions known for polysaccharides, and most involve simple sugars, usually reducing sugars. Glucose sugars chosen primarily because its activity has widespread appeal. Furthermore, determining the sugar content of food product may have industrial applications in aspects such as quality control.

One method to determine the sugar concentration of jam involves hydrolysis of the non-reducing sugarsto glucose, using sulphuric acid (H₂SO₄), after which the sample neutralized with sodium hydroxide (NaOH). When heated with 3,5-dinitrosalicylic acid (DNSA; also known as 2-hydroxy-3,5-dinitrobenzoic acid), reducing sugars (e.g. glucose and fructose) produce a red-brown product [6 - 8]. The concentration of the colored complex can be determined with the spectrophotometric method using wavelength 430 nm; the initial sugar concentration of the jam samples can then be read off a calibration curve created using known glucose concentrations.

Chemistry of 3, 5-Dinitrosalicylic acid

3,5-Dinitrosalicylic acid (DNSA) [IUPAC](#) name 2-hydroxy-3,5-dinitrobenzoic acid is an [aromatic compound](#) that reacts with [reducing sugars](#) and other reducing molecules to form [3-amino-5-nitrosalicylic acid](#), which strongly absorbs [light](#).

Structure and formula for 3, 5-Dinitrosalicylic acid

Linear Formula: (O₂N)₂C₆H₂-2-(OH)CO₂H

Experimental Section

Equipment and Chemicals

Double – beam Spectrophotometer model 6800, Cuvettes, Pipettes, 100 ml volumetric flasks, Conical flasks, Test tubes, Balance, Water bath, Funnel, Filter paper, Jam samples, DNSA reagent (3,5-dinitrosalicylic acid), Sulphuric acid (H₂SO₄) solution (approximately 2 mol/l), Sodium hydroxide (NaOH) solution (w=10%), Sodium potassium tartrate (NaK(CH₂OH)₂(COO)₂.4H₂O), Glucose powder (C₆H₁₂O₆)

3.2 Experimental Procedure

Preparation of solutions

DNSA reagent: To prepare the DNSA reagent, dissolve 10 g DNSA in 200 ml NaOH solution (about 2 mol/l). Heat the solution and stir thoroughly. Dissolve 300 g sodium potassium tartrate in 500 ml distilled water to form a colorstabilizer. Combine the two solutions, stir well and top up to 1 l with distilled water.

Jam (sugars): Weigh 1-2 g jam into a conical flask and add 10 ml sulphuric acid. Heat in a boiling water bath for 20 min, stirring periodically until hydrolysis is complete. Leave the sample to cool and carefully add 12 ml sodium hydroxide. Stir and filter into a 100 ml volumetric flask, and top up to 100 ml with distilled water. Using a pipette, transfer 10 ml solution into another 100 ml volumetric flask and top up to 100 ml with distilled water to produce the test solution. Stir well.

Jam (reducing sugars): Weigh 3.0 g jam into a conical flask, add 50 ml distilled water, heat and stir for 10 min. Filter into a 100 ml volumetric flask, and top up to 100 ml with distilled water. Using a pipette, transfer 10 ml solution into another 100 ml volumetric flask and top up to 100 ml with distilled water to produce the test solution. Stir well.

Stock glucose solution (15 mg/ml): Place 1.5 g glucose in a 100 ml volumetric flask and top up to 100 ml with distilled water. Stir.

Results and discussions

Creating the calibration curve

Mark five volumetric flasks (100 ml) with the letters A–E. Into each labelled flask, pipette the volumes of standard glucose solution and distilled water specified in Table 1.

Calculation of glucose concentration from spectrophotometer

Glucose concentration (mg/L) is: $(\text{Sample absorbance})/(\text{Standard absorbance}) \times 1000$

Table 1: Preparing the standard glucose solutions					
Flask	A	B	C	D	E
Volume of standard glucose solution (ml)	2	4	6	8	10
Volume of distilled water (ml)	98	96	94	92	90
Glucose concentration (mg/ml)	0.3	0.6	0.9	1.2	1.5

Label and fill six test tubes as specified in Table 2.

Table 2: Preparing the solutions for the calibration curve						
Sample number	Blank	1	2	3	4	5
Standard glucose solution (flask)	N/A	A	B	C	D	E
Volume of standard glucose solution (ml)	0	1	1	1	1	1
Volume of DNSA reagent (ml)	1	1	1	1	1	1
Volume of distilled water (ml)	3	2	2	2	2	2

3. Heat the test tubes and their contents in boiling water for 5 min; the DNSA reagent will react with any sugar present, producing a red-brown product.

4. Cool the test tubes, add 6 ml distilled water to each and shake well.

5. Using the wavelength 430 nm of the Double – beam Spectrophotometer model 6800, measure the transmittance of each solution.

Transmittances expressed in percentages and divided by 100 to obtain the transmittance values used in the subsequent calculations. Transmittance related to absorbance as described by the equation: $A = -\log T$ shown in Table 3.

The image to the right shows the calibration solutions; even the blank (water and DNSA with no glucose) is an intense color. It is therefore necessary to measure all the samples, including the blank, against distilled water.

The glucose-specific absorbance of the samples calculated by subtracting the absorbance measurement of the blank from the absorbance measurement of the sample in Table 3.

Table 3: Calibration curve – sample absorbance measurements of different concentrations of glucose solution			
Glucose concentration (mg/ml)	Transmittance %	Absorbance (A)	Glucose-specific absorbance ($A - A_{\text{blank}}$)
0 (Blank)	27.54	0.56	0
0.3	23.44	0.63	0.07
0.6	20.04	0.69	0.13
0.9	18.21	0.74	0.18
1.2	15.13	0.82	0.26
1.5	14.45	0.84	0.28

6. Plot glucose concentration against glucose-specific absorbance, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Sample calibration curve glucose-specific absorbance against concentration of glucose

7. Measuring the jam samples

The jam samples treated similarly to the glucose solutions used for the calibration curve.

For each jam test solution should be tested, put 1 ml prepared jam test solution in a test tube and add 1 ml DNSA reagent and 2 ml distilled water.

Heat the test tubes and their contents in boiling water for 5 min; the DNSA reagent will react with any sugar present, producing a red-brown product.

Cool the test tubes, add 6 ml distilled water to each and shake well.

8. Using the wavelength 430 nm of the spectrophotometer, measure the transmittance value (T%) of each jam sample. Divide by 100 to obtain T, convert T to A using the equation $A = -\log T$, and use that to calculate the glucose-specific absorbance ($A - A_{\text{blank}}$).

Table 4: Transmittance values obtained and the calculated glucose-specific absorbance of each sample.

Table 4: Sample results for jam samples			
Sample	Transmittance %	Absorbance (A)	Glucose specific absorbance ($A - A_{\text{blank}}$)
1	18.6	0.73	0.17
2	21.3	0.67	0.11

9. Using calibration curve, convert the absorbance measurements (A) into the concentrations of glucose (mg/ml) in prepared samples.

Using the examples from Table 4, the glucose concentrations read off the calibration curve give:

Sample 1: 0.8 mg/ml

Sample 2: 0.5 mg/ml

From the glucose concentrations, calculate the mass of glucose in a 1 g jam sample using the following equation:

$$\text{Mass glucose (g per 1g sample)} = \text{mass concentration (mg/ml)} \times 10 \times 100 \text{ ml}$$

where

Mass concentration is the value read off the calibration curve

10 is the dilution (Preparation of solutions)

100 ml is the volume of 1g of jam sample.

In our experiment,

$$\text{Sample 1: Mass of the glucose (g per 1g sample)} = 0.8 \text{ mg/ml} \times 10 \times 100 \text{ ml} = 0.8 \text{ g}$$

$$\text{Sample 2: Mass of the glucose (g per 1g sample)} = 0.5 \text{ mg/ml} \times 10 \times 100 \text{ ml} = 0.5 \text{ g.}$$

Conclusions

The spectrophotometric method offers an easy, less time consuming, sensitive analysis, by using simple and available reagents in the laboratory, used for determination of concentration of substances. Therefore, spectrophotometric analysis is one of the major interests of analytical laboratories as well as industries. This work represents the determination of mass of reducing sugar in jam by spectrophotometric method. A number of reactions between sugars and other chemical reagents produce colored products; the intensity of color related to the initial

concentration of sugar. The absorbance of sample solutions measured and compared to the absorbance of standard solutions of known sugar concentrations. Only a limited number of color-change reactions known for polysaccharides, and most involve simple sugars, usually reducing sugars. Glucose sugars chosen primarily because its activity has widespread appeal. Furthermore, determining the sugar content of jams may have industrial applications in aspects such as quality control. Mass concentration is the value read off the calibration curve. In our experiment, Sample 1 and Sample 2, Mass of the glucose found to be 0.8 g and 0.5 g.

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